

Studies in Quinoline Compounds. Part I.

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The object of this paper is to study a series of quinoline compounds with the view of discovering those that are likely to possess anti-protozoic and therapeutic properties.

Of the compounds described here, the first series contains a vinyl grouping. The presence of vinyl grouping in these compounds is comparable to the same group being present in quinine and allied compounds having therapeutic properties. These compounds possess certain definite properties, which are absent in the second series. They are generally yellow in colour and exhibit a blue fluorescence in dilute alcoholic solution. They are extremely insoluble in water, but dissolve fairly in alcohol, acetone and ether. They give a dark red colouration with acids. Their salts are hydrolysed in excess of water.

These compounds have been prepared from quinaldine and its derivatives by condensing them with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde. The reactivity of the α -methyl group in quinaldine has been taken advantage of in its condensation with this aldehyde. In the preparation of these compounds we have not taken the help of any condensing agent, as simply the heating of the reactants brings about their combination.

The second series of compounds have been obtained from the various aminoquinolines by condensing them with chloroacetamide. These compounds are not so much insoluble in water as compounds of the first series. They exhibit no fluorescence. Their salts are not hydrolysed by excess of water and they are generally colourless. Acids dissolve them without giving rise to any colour.

EXPERIMENTAL.

FIRST SERIES.

2-p-Dimethylaminostyrylquinoline.

Quinaldine (2 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (2 g.) are heated carefully in a dry test tube to gentle boiling for about 15 minutes over a small flame. The mixture is then dissolved in boiling alcohol and filtered. The filtrate on cooling deposits the above compound. It is then collected and dried (also *vide* Neolting and Witter, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 2479); m. p. 175°. (Found: N, 10.5. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2$ requires N, 10.2 per cent.).

6-Methyl-2-p-dimethylaminostyrylquinoline.

6-Methylquinaldine (1 g.) is mixed in a dry test tube with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1 g.) and the mixture heated carefully to gentle boiling over a small flame for about 15 minutes. The substance is purified and dried in the same way as in the previous case. It melted at 199°. (Found: N, 9.9. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.7 per cent.).

6-Oxy-2-p-dimethylaminostyrylquinoline.

6-Oxyquinaldine (2 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (2 g.) are mixed together and heated carefully to gentle boiling over a small flame for about 10 minutes. Acetone is then added in excess to the product. The hydroxy-derivative remains undissolved. It is separated and dried; m. p. above 240°. (Found: N, 9.89. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{ON}_2$ requires N, 9.65 per cent.).

6-Ethoxy-2-p-dimethylaminostyrylquinoline.

6-Ethoxyquinaldine (2 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (2 g.) are heated carefully to gentle boiling over a small flame for 10 minutes. The product is poured into water. The solid thus separated is then purified by recrystallisation from ether; m.p. 212°. (Found: N, 9.15. $C_{21}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 8.81 per cent.).

6-Methoxy-2-p-dimethylaminostyrylquinoline.

6-Methoxyquinaldine (2 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (2 g.) are condensed by heating for 15 minutes. The product is then dissolved in alcohol. Water precipitates the base from the alcoholic solution. It is then extracted with ether. The ethereal solution is then dried over fused calcium chloride and the ether removed. The residual solid thus obtained is then dried in vacuum; m.p. 202°. (Found: N, 9.45. $C_{20}H_{20}ON_2$ requires N, 9.2 per cent.).

SECOND SERIES.

Quinoline-6-aminoacetamide, $NH_2 \cdot CO \cdot CH_2 \cdot NH$

6-Aminoquinoline hydrochloride (4 g.) is dissolved in 20 c.c. of water and chloroacetamide (2.5 g.) added to it. The whole is then boiled for about 3 hours. It is then filtered, and the filtrate cooled with ice and made alkaline with a saturated solution of sodium carbonate, when the required compound separates out. It is filtered, recrystallised from alcohol and dried on a porous plate; m.p. 197°. (Found: N, 21.3. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2$ requires N, 20.9 per cent.).

Quinoline-8-aminoacetamide.

This compound is prepared by boiling a solution of 8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride and chloroacetamide in water in equimolecular proportions for 3 hours. The condensation product is then separated by adding sodium carbonate and then purified by recrystallising from alcohol; m.p. 183°. (Found: N, 21.25. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2$ requires N, 20.9 per cent.).

6-Ethoxyquinoline-8-aminoacetamide.

6-Ethoxy-8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride and chloroacetamide are dissolved in water in equimolecular proportions and the aqueous solution is boiled for 3 hours. The final product is isolated and purified as above; m.p. 235°. (Found: N, 16.88. $C_{13}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.1 per cent.).

6-Methoxyquinoline-8-aminoacetamide.

Equimolecular proportions of 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride and chloroacetamide are dissolved in water and the solution boiled for 3 hours. The product is separated and purified in the usual way; m.p. 226°. (Found: N, 17.89. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 18.2 per cent.).

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